

THE FREQUENCY OF OCCURRENCE OF PATIENTS WITH DENTAL DISEASES AMONG EMPLOYEES OF A CHEMICAL ENTERPRISE, THEIR SPECIFIC CLINIC AND COMPREHENSIVE TREATMENT MEASURES USING NEW MODERN MEDICINES.

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Annotation. The presence of high risks of occupational diseases among workers in industry has been proven. This is due to the entry of compounds of elements into the human body through the oral cavity (Lipanov G.Ya., Samylkin A.A., 2010; Adrianovsky V.I., 2015). Industrial workers are characterized by a high prevalence of dental caries and inflammatory periodontal diseases (Abdazimov A.D., 1990; Agafonov Yu.A., 2005; Kabirova M.F., 2013; Blashkova S.L., 2013).

Chemicals of the industrial air environment are detected in the oral fluid, hard tissues of teeth, dental deposits, biopsies of tissue structures (Khavkina E.Yu., 2008; Novikova E.N., 2009; Gazhva S.I., 2010; Olesova V.I. et al., 2012). They worsen the course of dental caries due to the substitution of calcium ions in hydroxyapatite crystals, chronic inflammation in periodontal tissues, violation of the integrity of the epithelium of the oral mucosa (Agafonov Yu.A., 2005).

key otters: industrial corrals, dental diseases, oil, gas, oral cavity

In our opinion, against the background of other dental diseases, the high incidence of COPD among industrial workers is associated, in our opinion, with harmful factors occurring in production, and reducing the impact of these harmful factors contributes to the reduction of these dental diseases.

The main reason for this conclusion is the fact that despite the fact that industrial workers are constantly under medical supervision, undergo medical examination once a year, despite the wide range of treatment options for identified diseases, including dental ones, the incidence of diseases of COPD is still high. Given the fact that this situation has a negative impact on the productivity of industrial workers, it is necessary to focus on preventive measures to reduce this situation within the framework of ongoing preventive measures.

When studying the condition of the hard tissues of the teeth, the main attention was paid to the occurrence of enamel hypoplasia (spots on the teeth). The results showed that there were practically no significant changes between

the compared groups in terms of the parameters for detecting enamel hypoplasia – respectively, this indicator was $1.1 \pm 0.6\%$ ($n = 14$) for industrial workers and $1.7 \pm 0.6\%$ ($n = 4$) for administrative workers.

These data show that the low incidence of enamel hypoplasia among production workers, regardless of work experience, does not require special preventive measures aimed at strengthening the hard tissues of the teeth, we consider it sufficient only to carry out generally accepted preventive measures to ensure oral health and dental health.

The study found that although dental services are provided among industry workers, it is done chaotically and does not meet today's requirements. Given the fact that the systematic implementation of dental care among industrial workers serves to prevent these diseases, there is a need to systematize dental care, develop and recommend certain regulations to improve its effectiveness. With this in mind, the chemical industry of Navoiyazot has begun to develop regulations for the provision of dental services.

To date, the absence of such regulations in the chemical industries of the country leads to low efficiency of dental services, including dental preventive medical examinations, as well as planning, improving the effectiveness of these measures, accurate assessment of the impact of adverse working conditions on the body, including the oral cavity.

Based on scientific sources and the results of personal research, we have developed regulations for the provision of dental care at Navoiyazot. The developed control algorithm is shown in Fig. 4.

The application of these regulations will make it possible to systematize the implementation of dental care among industrial workers, deduce the results of treatment and prevention, give specific recommendations to the employee to continue performing his official duties and ensure their legality. This reduces the likelihood of conflicts between employees and management, does not have a negative impact on labor productivity and allows employees to constantly monitor the condition of their teeth.

Dental examination during a medical examination

Dental diagnosis and treatment
according to the

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Carrying out dental prophylaxis

Dentist's conclusion on treatment and prevention

The conclusion of the medical and sanitary part of the enterprise on the status of the employee, his profession or transfer to another job

employees of the chemical industry systematizes the treatment and prevention of dental diseases, which allows you to constantly monitor the condition of your teeth. By reducing the dental morbidity of industrial workers, they reduce the overall morbidity, ensuring a high level of employee health.

Social significance

The regulation on the provision of dental services among chemical industry workers will improve the efficiency of this service by systematizing their medical care, including dental care, which will increase labor productivity and also have a positive impact on the quality of life of employees.

Conclusions:

1. It has been established that the occurrence of the main symptoms of dental diseases among employees of the Navoiyazot industry is higher than among employees of the administration of this chemical industry. Of the 9 indicators identified, 8 turned out to be 1.5-7.6 times more common in industrial workers. Symptoms that differed significantly and required attention when

planning preventive measures included increased sensitivity of teeth to food and sweets (7.6 and 6.1 times), bleeding gums (6.2 times), discomfort in the oral cavity (7.4 times).

2. Among industrial workers, 69.1% of all those involved in the study did not have pathological changes in the SOPR, while this indicator was 85.7% among administration workers. It was found that SOPR is statistically significant among industrial workers: gingivitis in workers is 1.9 times more common, stomatitis - 2.2 times, candidiasis - 5.4 times. Against the background of other dental diseases, the high incidence of COPD among industrial workers is due to harmful factors found in industry.

3. Pulpitis and periodontitis were diagnosed from inflammatory diseases of the dental system ($48.8 \pm 3.0\%$ and $22.9 \pm 2.6\%$, respectively, in industrial workers - $4.85 \pm 2.4\%$ and $20.7 \pm 1.4\%$). There is no convincing difference between the above parameters. Against the background of the absence of OCD in industrial workers (0%), malocclusion was detected in $16.0 \pm 2.3\%$ of cases, in $84.0 \pm 2.3\%$ of cases, the development of the maxillary system was normal.

4. There were no practically convincing changes among the compared groups in terms of the parameters for detecting enamel hypoplasia - respectively, this indicator was $1.1 \pm 0.6\%$ for industrial workers and $1.7 \pm 0.6\%$ for administrative workers. The low incidence of enamel hypoplasia among industrial workers, regardless of work experience, does not require special preventive measures aimed at strengthening the hard tissues of the teeth, we believe that it is sufficient only if generally accepted preventive measures are followed to ensure the health of the oral cavity and teeth.

5. In order to systematize and improve the efficiency of providing dental services to employees of the Navoiyot industry The regulations for the provision of dental services have been developed.

Recommendations for implementation

Methodological recommendations have been implemented in the practical activities of the Bukhara Regional Medical Association and the Kagan Regional Medical Association.

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